

Practice abstract #2

Involving rural communities in the design of solar-powered water desalination systems

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Framing and context

The analysis of **La Graciosa** revealed two major structural challenges affecting infrastructure development on rural islands. First, **local decision-making capacity is limited**. Although La Graciosa is recognised as an inhabited island, it remains administratively dependent on the municipality of Teguise and other external authorities. As a result, **key**

infrastructure decisions related to water, energy, and environmental management **require coordination across multiple administrative levels**, including municipal, insular, regional, and national institutions. This fragmented governance structure significantly slows decision-making and implementation processes.

Second, **the regulatory framework is highly complex** due to the island's extensive environmental protections. La Graciosa is part of a Natural Park, a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve, and the Natura 2000 network, which means that infrastructure projects must pass through multiple permitting procedures and environmental assessments. Together, **these governance and regulatory barriers make the deployment of essential infrastructure, such as renewable-powered desalination systems, technically and administratively challenging.**

This practice abstract presents a **methodology for designing solar water desalination systems in a small island community** through contextual analysis and multi-actor engagement. In La Graciosa (Canary Islands), the approach combines desk research, stakeholder consultations, and technical feasibility studies to align infrastructure design with local environmental, regulatory, and social conditions. Local actors, including the energy community and municipal authorities, are involved early to validate needs, identify constraints, and guide system parameters such as water sources, production capacity, and site selection. **This process helps ensure that desalination solutions respond to real community needs** while remaining technically feasible within a highly protected natural environment.

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Objectives

- To integrate **local knowledge and priorities** through engagement with community actors, local authorities, and technical partners, ensuring that the desalination solution responds to real water needs and local operational capacities.
- To design a solar water desalination system that is technically **adapted** to the environmental, climatic, and infrastructural conditions of a highly constrained **island environment**.
- To ensure that the proposed solution can be implemented within the complex regulatory and environmental **framework governing protected island territories**.

Methodological approach

The methodological approach combines contextual analysis, stakeholder engagement, and technical feasibility assessment. First, **desk research** was conducted to analyse existing studies, datasets, regulatory frameworks, and environmental constraints relevant to water, energy, and infrastructure on La Graciosa. Second, **consultations with local actors**, including municipal authorities, the water consortium, and the local energy community, were carried out to incorporate community knowledge and validate local needs and constraints. Third, **preliminary technical feasibility studies** were performed to evaluate water availability, solar energy potential, and desalination system design parameters. The methodology remains **exploratory**, as final system specifications will be refined following detailed site surveys and water quality analysis.

The methodological approach involves **several institutional, technical, and community stakeholders**. Local participants include representatives of the energy community El Sol de La Graciosa, the municipality of Tegui, the Lanzarote Water Consortium, and the Government of the Canary Islands. The work is **supported by project partners and research organisations**, including the technology provider - Boreal Light GmbH, as well as

University of Galway, and R2M Solution Spain SL, which contributes to coordination and organisational aspects of the project. In addition, Traza contributes social and territorial analyses to support the understanding of local community dynamics and contextual conditions relevant to the project.

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Emerging insights

- The analysis confirms that **water security is a critical issue for La Graciosa** due to extreme aridity, dependence on external desalination from Lanzarote, and frequent infrastructure failures. Local renewable-powered desalination could significantly improve resilience.
- **Fragmented governance and complex permitting processes** across multiple administrative levels represent a major barrier to implementing essential infrastructure projects in protected island territories.
- Early **involvement of local actors**, such as the energy community and municipal authorities, appears essential to **ensure public acceptance**, adapt solutions to local realities, and facilitate coordination between institutions during project implementation.

The knowledge generated through this methodology can **support the planning and deployment of resilient water and energy infrastructure in small island** environments facing water scarcity, fragile supply systems, and complex regulatory frameworks. The approach demonstrates how contextual analysis, stakeholder engagement, and technical feasibility studies can guide the development of renewable-powered desalination systems adapted to environmentally protected territories. This knowledge **can inform engineers, infrastructure developers, and project planners** working on sustainable water solutions, as well as policymakers responsible for island governance and environmental permitting. It can also support local communities and energy associations seeking to strengthen water security and energy independence through locally adapted renewable technologies.

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